

Antibacterial Activity of Actinomycetes Isolated from a Few Selected Soil Samples of Southern Region of Western Ghats

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Abstract— Soil, actinomycetes plays an important role in pharmaceutical industries because they produce valuable natural antibiotics to treat chronic diseases in humans. In the present study, the actinomycetes were isolated from four different sample sites of Western Ghats. Totally twelve isolates were selected and screened for antibiotic activity using coliforms. Among the twelve isolates, two were found to effective against coliforms and these isolates were obtained from soil of Courtallum. Antibiotic sensitivity of the twelve isolates revealed varying performance. The two actinomycetes isolates of Courtallum have a potential to be included in researches of new preparations with characterization of the bioactive compounds.

Keywords— Actinomycete; Antibiotic; Coliform; Bioactive compounds.

I. INTRODUCTION

Microbial population plays a prominent role in biotechnology and pharmaceutical industries as it offers countless new genes and biochemical pathways to probe for medically and industrially useful compounds. There are a number of microorganisms which produce a number of which are primarily bioactive secondary metabolites.

Soil is a reservoir of microorganisms and the inhabitants of soil produce many useful bioactive natural products which include important antibiotics. Among the soil microbes, Actinomycetes are important and they account for a high proportion of soil microbial biomass next to bacteria in abundance. They are diverse group of gram positive bacteria and are the most economically and biotechnologically valuable prokaryotes. The secondary metabolites of streptomycetes have found industrial applications as antibiotics as well as antifungal, antiparasitic, antitumor and immunosuppressive drugs, among others (Schrempf and Dyson, 2011). The molecular structures of these compounds are diverse and have usually low toxicity which renders them good candidates for drug development (Bérdy, 2005). A range of industrially important enzymes are also produced, as well as enzyme inhibitors and insecticides (Goodfellow and Williams, 1986).

In the recent past, problems of drug resistance, resistance of organisms to multiple number of drugs, sensitivity of patients and inability to control certain infectious diseases have given an impetus for continuous search of new antimicrobial drugs from new sources.

Because of this, many pharmaceutical industry and scientists have actively involved in the isolation and screening of actinomycetes from different habitats for their production of antimicrobial compounds. So, this study was attempted to isolate and screen actinomycetes from a few selected soil of

southern region of Western Ghats for antibacterial activity with the following objectives.

- Isolation of actinomycetes from soils collected from the southern region of Western Ghats.
- Preliminary screening of actinomycetes isolates against bacterial strains by cross streak method.
- Secondary screening of actinomycetes isolates against bacterial strains by well diffusion method.
- Determination of antibiotic tolerance for the actinomycete isolates

II. MATERIALS AND METHODS

The soil samples were collected from the following sites Courtallum (main falls-10°04'N 77°45'E), Ooty (botanical garden-11-49N, 76.0 E to 77.15 E), Palakad (Mamalamphuzadam-10°49'55.0"N 76°40'58.7"E) and Theni (Kumbakkarai falls-10°10'48"N 77°31'50"E) of Tamil Nadu. Samples were collected 5cm below the soil surface and they were taken aseptically using sterile spatula and scalpel into sterile polyethylene bags. Samples were brought to laboratory in aseptic condition and stored in the refrigerator at 4° C until use. Just before isolation, soil samples were heated for 1 hour at 50 – 55° C in oven (Cross and Atwell, 1974).

Media and Reagents used

Composition of various media and reagents are given in Appendix

Isolation of Actinomycetes (Subathra Devi et al., 2013)

One gram of pretreated soil sample was mixed with 99ml of sterile distilled water. The suspension was mixed thoroughly and serially diluted up to 10⁻⁵ dilution. From 10⁻³, 10⁻⁴ and 10⁻⁵ dilutions, 0.1ml was separately spread on Kuster's agar plates in duplicate and incubated at 27° C for 7 days. After the incubation period, the plates examined for the presence of actinomycetes colonies and the colonies were sub cultured and maintained as slants for further study.

Biochemical Characterization

A smear of culture was taken in a clean glass slide and heated gently over a flame. Add few drops of crystal violet for 1min and washed with tap water. Now, flood Gram’s iodine solution for 1 min and washed with tap water, following that few drops of decolorizing agent (ethyl alcohol 95%) was added until the violet colour ceased to flow away. The slide was washed with water and counter stain safranin was flooded over the smear for 2 min, then the slide was washed, drained, air dried, and viewed under microscope. The culture retaining the violet colour indicated that it was gram positive organism.

Collecton and Maintainance of Bacterial Cultures

The bacterial cultures *Enterobacteraerogenes* and *Escherichia coli* were collected from Divison of Microbiology, CLRI, Chennai. The cultures were confidrmmedusing EMB (Eosin Methylene Blue) agar medium. Fresh culture was obtained by growing them in nutrient broth and used for preliminary and secondary screening.

Preliminary Screening of Actinomycete Isolates for Antibacterial Activity (SubathraDevi et al., 2013)

The actinomycetesisolates were subjected to primary screening by cross streak technique using *E.aerogenes* and *E.coli* as test organisms. Straight- line inoculation of the actinomycetes isolates was made on CSPY (Casein Starch Peptone Yeast) medium and incubated at 28° C for 4 days. After incubation the test organisms were streaked at right angles of actinomycetes culture and incubated at 37° C. Based on the inhibition zone, measured after 24-48 hours, the antagonistic actinomycetes were selected for secondary screening.

Secondary Screening of Actinomycete Isolates for Antibacterial Activity by Agar Well Diffusion Method (Subathra Devi et al., 2013)

The actinomycete isolates were grown in CSPY broth for 4 days and the crude culture filtrate was analyzed by agar well diffusion method. Broth cultures of *E. aerogenes* and *E. coli* were swabbed onto the surface of Mueller- Hinton agar plates and allowed to dry. Using sterile cork borer, wells (5mm diameter) were made on the agar plates and 100 µL of culture filtrate was loaded into the well. All the plates were incubated at 37°C for 24 hours and the zone of inhibition was measured in mm.

Antibiotic Sensitivity Pattern of Actinomycete Isolates (Febina Bernice Sharon and Kalidass, 2014)

Antibiotic sensitivity pattern of actinomycete isolates was determined by growing a lawn culture of them in ISP7 medium and challenged against eight commercially available antibiotic discs of Ampicillin, Chloramphenicol, Gentamycin, Kanamycin, Methicillin, PenicillinG, Rifampicin, and Vancomycin. The discs were aseptically placed on the surface of agar medium, incubated at 28° C for 48 hours and zone of inhibition was measured.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

The present scenario demands the discovery of new antimicrobial agents, with better potential and broad spectrum activity, against multidrug resistant microbes than the

previously discovered agents. The reason for this demand is the emergence of the new kind of common pathogens which are multidrug resistant. To solve these problems, it is an alarm to the researchers to discover new discover new drugs from biological sources with the options of no side effects and target oriented activity. The present study is focused on isolation of actinomycetes from soil sample samples of four locations in southern region of Western Ghats.

The soil samples were checked for pH and it was found to be in the range of 7.0-8.0 (Table I). This pH range is known to support the growth of actinomycetes in soil of different geographical locations. In the present study, actinomycetes were isolated from four different soil samples by serial dilution method using Kuster's agar medium and the enumeration of the actinomycetes colonies was done (Table II). Based on antibiotics (clear zone around the actinomycetes colony), twelve colonies were selected as isolates and they were given the code as C1, C2, C3, O1, O2, O3,O4, O5, P1, P2, T1, and T2 (Table IV). These isolates were characterized morphologically for colour of aerial mycelium, reverse side colour and production of diffusible pigments.

TABLE I. Soil characteristics.

Soil sample	pH range
Courtallam	8.02
Ooty	6.70
Palakkad	7.82
Theni	7.95

TABLE II. Total CFU count.

Soil samples	No. of colony cfu/ml		
	10 ⁻³	10 ⁻⁴	10 ⁻⁵
Courtallam	60×10 ⁻³	40×10 ⁻⁴	10×10 ⁻⁵
Ooty	210×10 ⁻³	160×10 ⁻⁴	40×10 ⁻⁵
Palakad	200×10 ⁻³	70×10 ⁻⁴	30×10 ⁻⁵
Theni	90×10 ⁻³	30×10 ⁻⁴	10×10 ⁻⁵

TABLE III. Colony characterization.

Soil sample	Colour	Reverse colour	Diffusible pigment
Courtallam	Ash white	Yellow	Absence of pigment
	Green	Black	Absence of pigment
	White with yellow colouration	Yellow	Yellow
Ooty	Dark ash	Yellow brown	Absence of pigment
	Green	Black	Absence of pigment
	Light ash	Yellow	Absence of pigment
	Pink with yellow colouration	Yellow	Yellow
	White dotted colony	Orange yellow	Light yellow
Palakkad	Pink	Yellow	Absence of pigment
	Black with brown colouration	Brown	Brown
Theni	Pink	Orange yellow	Absence of pigment
	White with yellow colouration	Yellow	Yellow

Among the twelve isolates, two were green; two were pink; and two were white with yellow in coloration. Reverse side colour varied with the isolates and five isolates showed diffusible pigment production (Table III).

TABLE IV. Antibacterial activity of actinomycetes isolates against coliforms.

Soil sampling site	Isolates	Zone of inhibition against bacterial coliforms (cm)	
		<i>Enterobacter aerogenes</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>
Courtallam	C1	1.2	1.3
	C2	1.2	1.1
	C3	1.1	-
Ooty	O1	-	-
	O2	-	-
	O3	-	-
	O4	1	-
	O5	-	-
Palakkad	P1	-	-
	P2	-	-
Theni	T1	-	-
	T2	-	-

Preliminary and secondary screening methods were used to screen the actinomycetes isolates for antibacterial activity. In this study, coliforms such as *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacterogenes* were used as test organisms. In preliminary screening, all the isolates inhibited growth of *E. coli*, but not *E. aerogenes* which exhibited mucoid growth in the growth medium used for preliminary screening. Out of 12, only 2 (16.6 %) isolates of actinomycetes (C1 and C2) showed antibacterial activity against coliforms in secondary screening and the ten isolates did not inhibit growth of coliforms. This difference could be due to the chemical modification of the active compounds to become inactive in the media used (Gurung *et al.*, 2009). In this study, CSPY medium and Muller Hinton agar media used for preliminary and secondary respectively. From the results of secondary screening (Table IV) it is clear that the isolates C1 and C2 showed better inhibition than other isolates and it could be due to the production of more than other isolates and it could be due to

the production of more than one antibacterial metabolites that made the isolates effective inhibitors to *Escherichia coli* and *Enterobacter aerogenes*.

IV. CONCLUSION

The results of this study indicate a varied performance with the isolates of actinomycetes. The twelve isolates tested for antibiotic sensitivity, P1 and P2 were found to be sensitive to all the antibiotics used; C1, C2, O2, O5 were sensitive to seven antibiotics; C2 was sensitive to six antibiotics; O4 and T2 were sensitive to five antibiotics. Actinomycetes O3 was found to be sensitive only to two antibiotics.

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